

Training Needs Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Human Resource Management is the organizational function that deals with issues related to people such as compensation, hiring, performance management, organization development, safety, wellness, benefits, employee motivation, communication, administration, and training.

Newly appointed people must be first trained in the organization. This training has to be done properly, clearly and neatly.

The new process of training is to analyze the new people who have joined the organization for working. Analyzing the new people may help to what actually training the people required for working. This will stop the waste of time as people may know the same thing earlier.

Keywords: Training Needs Analysis, organization, employee, skills, knowledge.

I. INTRODUCTION

When new employees are appointed in the organization, it is necessary to give the advanced training according to their job. Training refers to obtain the skills, knowledge, and ability about the specific work in the organization as a result of training teaching of verbal and practical skills, which are used for work.

As the training of new employees should enhance beyond the initial qualifications to upgrade the skills of employees better than previous. This training may lead to the occupation development.

Training Needs

A Training Needs Analysis can be performed to achieve a variety of objectives. The survey can be undertaken at a number of levels within an organization:

Organizational Needs

The Human Resources department may wish to undertake a Training Needs Analysis to gauge if staffs have the knowledge and skills necessary to meet the organization's strategic objectives. Important decisions like whether to recruit new talent or enhance the skills of current employees are based on this knowledge.

Project, Department or Area of Work

Employees may become involved in new areas of work or on projects which make new demands on them and require different skills. A Training Needs Analysis can identify if employees' current skills can meet these new demands and highlight key areas for development.

Individual Needs

Appraisals may identify a need to improve an individual's performance in their existing role, a need for development so they can meet new challenges or new departmental needs. Our Training Needs Analysis will enable managers to identify these individual needs amongst their employees.

Advantages of Training

Training to employees keeps the employees updated as the industry work changes. That keeps them in touch with all the newly arrived technologies. Training also helps to see the weakness and fill the gaps. The main and the important thing that training

help is the employees are provided with the promotions which satisfy their job needs.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Training needs and analysis is the new approach to be examined and applied in the organizations for the proper analyzed training to the employees.

Till the date, all the employees are treated as same and they are trained together.

All employees have trained the same study with no studies on the employees what they require and what they don't. This may waste the time as well as money of both organization and employees.

III. OBJECTIVE

1. Trainee training needs.
2. To analysis training needs to employee

Training Needs Analysis Purpose

A Training Needs Analysis (TNA) is used to estimate an organization's training needs. Gap analysis is the root of the training needs analysis. This is a calculation of the gap the between knowledge, skills, and attitudes of the employees in the organization which they are learning in the organization to meet the organization's objectives. This process is best conducted before the planning the training process like budgeting, designing and performing. The output of the needs analysis will be kept in a document that specifies why, what, who, when, where and how.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Training Need Analysis

The purpose of training needs analysis is to determine what employees required for effective performance. Training need analysis is conducted whether the all resources required for the training purpose are available or not.

This helps an organization to plan the total training process such as the budget for training, areas where training is effective and required and this may help to change the actions taking in the training process.

The following points must be kept in view:

1. The methods which are used for training should be sometimes used in combination, but there should not be relevant to one particular method.
2. The methods may be used to identify needs of each of the various employees.

3. Employees should be personally asked what to train and what not to train as he may know the same thing previously.

They should be applied to individual employees since training needs will change from employee to employee.

V. CONCLUSION

The training process of the newly appointed employees should be changed as the study of the employees to be done and framing what they actually need where they want to improve and where they want to need to work in the organization. This will help to save the important and valuable time and money for both employees and organization.

VI. RECOMMENDATIONS

Understanding the employee's expectations and taking proper feedback from employees can help to proper training. Proper availability of the resources, tools, and information is part of a training may lead to better performance. Designing the training plan and the motivation training for the employees helps in developing skills and the knowledge of employees.

VII. REFERENCES

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